

THE EXPRESSION OF COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Aliboeva Nilufar Makhamatali kizi

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

EFL Teacher at Kokand branch of Tashkent State Technical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7223370>

Abstract. *Comparative analysis is the process of comparing items and identifying similarities and differences. When a company wants to analyze an idea, problem, theory, or question, conducting a comparative analysis allows it to better understand the issue and develop strategies to address it.*

Keywords and expressions: *comparison words, analysis, conjunctions, competitive.*

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОГО АНАЛИЗА

Аннотация. *Сравнительный анализ представляет собой процесс сравнения предметов и выявления сходств и различий. Когда компания хочет проанализировать идею, проблему, теорию или вопрос, проведение сравнительного анализа позволяет ей лучше понять проблему и разработать стратегии для ее решения.*

Ключевые слова и выражения: *слова-сравнения, анализ, союзы, конкуренты.*

INTRODUCTION

A company might use this type of analysis to examine items with obvious differences or items with both differences and similarities. For example, a healthcare company may use this analysis to compare and contrast two different types of medications. Other businesses may conduct a comparative analysis to determine which of two different production processes is more efficient. A company will typically conduct a comparative analysis to determine:

The strategies of competitors, both indirect and direct

a company's financial health, including its investments and profit margins.

budgets are examples of accounting strategies.

how trends affect a specific audience

new opportunities in technology, marketing, or related fields

Comparative analyses

Comparative analyses are necessary to gain a better understanding of a problem or to answer pertinent questions. The following are the primary goals that businesses hope to achieve by comparing data sets, documents, or processes: giving data a frame of reference.

A comparative analysis describes how data or processes differ from one another and how they are related. This provides context for the analysis, making it easier to see the differences and similarities in the relationships between data sets. For instance, an automaker may compare the safety features of two or more models to see how they affect sales or which features need to be improved. This type of analysis may provide detailed data on each feature as well as historical data to compare how each feature performs.

A successful comparative analysis also assists a company in developing substantial and meaningful reasons for conducting the comparison. The information gathered by a company for a comparative analysis to support claims or arguments is not haphazard, but rather thoroughly researched evidence. The purpose of an analysis could be to present opposing arguments and examine both sides, or to prove or disprove an argument. For example, an automaker's analysis could show that certain safety features increase auto sales. The analysis provides and confirms

data indicating that side airbags are more popular than traction control. This enables a manufacturer to concentrate on improving and publicizing the features that customers want when purchasing a new car.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The difference of comparative and competitive analyses

The distinction between comparative and competitive analyses is based on the company's motivation for conducting either study. A comparative analysis, for example, could provide a comparison of indirect and direct competition to form an overall view of an entire market. To provide general information from a large population, this process relies on quantitative data. Comparative analysis examples include:

Pattern analysis

Pattern analysis: Identifies patterns of behavior or trends to make predictions or enforce probability

Data filtering: Analyzes group data to identify and extract data subsets

Decision tree: Analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of a decision through its influences and risks

Competitive analyses examine a specific direct competitor in order to provide side-by-side comparisons. To narrow the similarities and differences between your company and a competitor, you could conduct qualitative research. A competitive analysis examines the services, marketing strategies, and reputation of a direct competitor. A company, for example, may use a competitive analysis to compare and identify the best business structure to use, such as a sole proprietorship, limited liability company (LLC), or corporation.

Consider the following suggestions for conducting an effective comparative analysis: In order to conduct a comparative analysis, it is critical to conduct extensive research. Conducting research not only provides evidence to back up your findings, but it may also present a new perspective or angle not previously considered. Research may also provide insight into how competitors may approach a problem. Consider making a detailed list of similarities and differences when comparing two things in a comparative analysis.

Consider making a detailed list of similarities and differences when comparing two things in a comparative analysis. Determine how changing one aspect affects another, such as how increasing the number of employee vacation days affects sales, production, or costs. A comparative analysis can also aid in the identification of external causes such as economic conditions or environmental issues.

CONCLUSION

Although a comparative analysis may seek to support one argument or idea over another, it is critical that the analysis detail both sides equally. Although a comparative analysis may seek to support one argument or idea over another, it is critical that the analysis detail both sides equally. To make informed, practical decisions or develop alternative solutions, an analysis comparing the benefits and drawbacks of starting a recycling program might examine its benefits, such as corporate responsibility, as well as its potential negative impacts, such as high implementation costs.

REFERENCES

1. TZ Mukumovna, Tasks and problems of acquisition of words from English into uzbek, Web of Scientist: International Scientific research journal 3(5),1642-1645,2022
2. Ismoilova Kamola Rafikovna, The theoretical approaches to the study of metaphor in a cognitive aspect, International journal of early childhood special education (INT-JECS), Issue 04 2022.
3. O'sarova Nilufar Yakubovna, The role of the teacher in the development of young student's self-knowledge, Eurasian Journal of social sciences, philosophy and culture, ISSN 2181-2888, April 2022, 45-48.
4. Alimjon Tojiyev, Farkhad Usmanov. SYNCRETISM IN VERB-NOUN COGNATE WORDS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. JCR. 2020; 7(14): 3321-3331. doi:10.31838/jcr.07.14.610
5. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/comparative-analysis>
6. T Z.M, Thematics journal of English language teaching, Innovative approaches to the assessment of student project works, 6(ISSN 2231-4873), 99-104,2022